

Experimental Comparison of Additively Manufactured Premixed Hydrogen Burners using Optical Diagnostics

Sebastian R. Faderl^{a,b}, Nikolas Schmidt^a, Fabian Töpfer^a, Raphael Strickling^c, Julian Schrauder^{d,b}, Dominic Bartels^{d,b}, Faizan Habib Vance^c, Michael Schmidt^{d,b}, Arne Scholtissek^c, Florian J. Bauer^{a,b}, Stefan Will^{a,b,*}

^a*Lehrstuhl für Technische Thermodynamik (LTT), Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU), Am Weichselgarten 8, Erlangen, 91058, Bayern, Germany*

^b*Erlangen Graduate School in Advanced Optical Technologies (SAOT), Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU), Paul-Gordan-Straße 6, Erlangen, 91052, Bayern, Germany*

^c*Simulation of Reactive Thermo-Fluid Systems (STFS), TU Darmstadt, Otto-Berndt-Str. 2, Darmstadt, 64287, Hessen, Germany*

^d*Lehrstuhl für Photonische Technologien (LPT), Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Konrad-Zuse-Straße 3/5, Erlangen, 91052, Bayern, Germany*

Abstract

Premixed hydrogen combustion is increasingly important as a technology for decarbonizing high-temperature industrial processes. The design flexibility enabled by additive manufacturing provides new opportunities to realize complex burner geometries that are difficult or impossible to produce with conventional methods. By coupling it with geometry optimization based on numerical simulations, the development of burners with increased stability, extended fuel and power flexibility, and reduced pollutant emissions becomes possible. In this study, three different modular burner nozzle designs are systematically compared with respect to these optimization targets using a newly developed diagnostic framework. Distinct differences between the nozzle configurations are identified in terms of their operational range, as characterized by flame stability maps. Simultaneous OH and CH₂O planar laser-induced fluorescence (PLIF), in combination with OH* chemiluminescence measurements, are employed to analyze the main location of heat release. Complementary infrared measurements of both the nozzle and the flame temperature (at a fixed location in the flames) reveal strong correlations between flame stability characteristics, heat release location, and a possible feedback into the nozzle material. We conclude that these mainly result from the difference between the local mixture distribution of the nozzles. Based on this experimental framework, the characterization and evaluation of optimized design geometries become possible.

Keywords: Hydrogen Combustion, Additive Manufacturing, High-Speed Chemiluminescence, Planar Laser-Induced Fluorescence, Infrared Thermometry

1. Introduction

Many countries around the world are actively pursuing decarbonization by incorporating hydrogen into their national energy strategies, e.g. India [1], China [2], Japan [3] and Chile [4]. Also the European Union has identified it as one of the key components for their strategy in decarbonizing the industries of European countries [5]. This resulted in several programs for the roll-out of hydrogen production, infrastructure and end-use-technologies, including the European Green Deal [6]. Hydrogen combustion is receiving increasing attention for high-temperature applications, particularly in energy conversion [7, 8] and provision of industrial process heat [9, 10]. Gas turbines represent a key technology in these sectors and are traditionally fueled by natural gas (primarily methane). Currently, major gas turbine manufacturers [11, 12, 13, 14] are actively developing systems capable of operating with hydrogen–methane blends as well as pure hydrogen. Another important sector for hydrogen combustion are industrial-grade burners,

*corresponding author

Email address: stefan.will@fau.de (Stefan Will)

which are often highly specialized and range from low-emission MILD burners operating at tens of kilowatts [15] to multi-megawatt burners for, e.g., the steel industry [16].

Hydrogen as a fuel poses several challenges such as high laminar flame speeds, high molecular diffusivity due to its small molecular weight [17, 18] and high adiabatic flame temperatures [19]. On the one hand, these combustion characteristics can negatively affect flame stability, flash-back, and flammability limits. Another issue are the NO_x emissions caused by the high flame temperatures [20]. On the other hand, these characteristics can be advantageous, e.g., the lower ignition temperature leads to broader operating ranges and the high temperatures can increase the burning efficiency [21]. The high flame speed and reactivity also enable very lean combustion regimes without lean blow-outs of the flame, which can be useful for stability and pollutant reduction [20, 22, 23]. To address the aforementioned challenges of hydrogen as a fuel, the usage of premixed combustion in micromix burners has been brought into the focus of recent research [14, 24, 25]. By dividing the burner into multiple smaller flames with lower power, the NO_x emissions can be significantly improved. Smaller flames can also be more easily controlled and the effect of flash-backs on the burner will be reduced. A successful nozzle design must deliver wide operability across fuels and power levels, minimize pollutant emissions, and ensure flash-back-safe operation [24]. This study is based on the concept of decreasing the premixing volume and therefore the ignitable fuel/air mixture, by mixing fuel and oxidizer close to the burner nozzle outlet. By introducing a bluff-body downstream of the location, where fuel and air flows are combined, a high degree of mixing can be ensured. This can directly increase flame stability and lower the NO_x formation, as was investigated by Schmidt et al. [26]. This was also explored by Vance and Scholtissek [27], who introduced a radial stratification of the mixture fields to mitigate the flash-back propensity of premixed flames. In this context, stratification refers to local variations in the fuel/air mixture, whereby fuel-rich central flows are typically surrounded by lean peripheral flows. In case of the present work, the stratification is largely affected and controlled by the bluff-body geometry.

The aim of this study is the experimental comparison of compact, modular, premixed burners with optimized geometries derived from numerical simulations. Due to the sensitivity of the mixture field on bluff-body geometry, shape optimization of the nozzle-internal geometry has a high potential for burner optimization with respect to stability, flexibility and pollutant reduction. Employing additive manufacturing (AM) for the numerically optimized nozzle geometries, three different nozzles are compared in this study. Optical diagnostics are used to investigate the flame topology, heat release rate (HRR), flame temperatures T_{Flm} , and nozzle temperatures T_{Noz} , with the goal of identifying beneficial design elements. First, the operational limits for the different nozzles are determined, showing significant differences. To elucidate the underlying causes of these differences, measurements of T_{Noz} are performed. From the latter, first trends reveal that the location of the maximum HRR (LMHR) and the thermal feedback into the nozzle, resulting from the differences in the mixture fields, are a major influence on the extinction limits. To verify this, simultaneous OH and CH_2O planar laser-induced fluorescence (PLIF) is used, which scales with the local abundance of these radicals in the flame. The HRR can be calculated from the overlap of both images, as demonstrated by Paul and Najm [28]. As there is no CH_2O in pure hydrogen flames, another marker for the HRR is needed and was found in the OH^* radical [29, 30], which is then visualized utilizing high-speed chemiluminescence recordings. From these images, a semi-quantitative parameter in form of the C/L-ratio is determined to discuss the trends in the LMHR of each nozzle. The trends in the LMHR are extended by measuring the flame temperature at a fixed height above the burner (HAB) to achieve comparability between the nozzles. Finally, the flame temperatures are linked to pollutant emissions, as one of the main mechanisms of NO_x formation in hydrogen flames is the Zeldovich-mechanism, driven by high temperatures [31]. The NO_x emissions are measured, to ultimately link the effect of the shape optimization on pollutant formation.

2. Burner Setup

2.1. Basic Nozzle Principle

The nozzle design is based on Schmidt et al. [26] and is depicted in Figure 1. It consists of an inner lance (1) with an inner diameter of 4 mm, supplying fuel into the nozzle through hexagonally arranged outlets. In the surrounding tube (2), which has an inner diameter of 15 mm, the oxidizer is supplied. Both gas streams are mainly mixed behind the bluff-body (3) due to a recirculation inside the outer nozzle (4). The nozzle outlet has a diameter of 7.5 mm. The air-supply is homogenized by the use of three copper foam discs of 10 mm thickness (5). The design

is highly modular, all parts can be quickly changed for different geometrical configurations. This is coupled with the possibilities for rapid prototyping provided by AM, enabling measurements on a variety of different nozzles, with the three investigated configurations pictured in Figure 1 and labeled N00, N01 and N02, respectively. The choice of these nozzle configurations are based on the reference design of Schmidt et al. [26] for N00, and nozzles resulting from the shape optimization with different levels of stratification for N01 and N02 (see upcoming section 2.2). The setup is consistent after changing the parts, which ensures repeatability for the diagnostics applied. The technical premixing of the gases within the nozzle results in a smaller volume of ignitable gases compared to most conventional premixed burners. This design significantly reduces damage caused by potential flash-backs. Another approach is to delay flash-back by stratifying the local mixture field at the burner outlet [27]. Furthermore, the burner was designed with a high degree of operational flexibility in terms of both fuel composition and power output. It is capable of operating with pure H_2 , H_2/CH_4 , and hydrogen–ammonia (H_2/NH_3) mixtures. The present study, however, focuses on pure hydrogen and its blends with methane. The mass-flow of the gases into the nozzle is controlled by three Bronkhorst mass-flow controllers (MFCs). The manufacturer specifies the accuracy to $\pm 0.5\%$ of the reading and $\pm 0.1\%$ of the full scale. The MFCs have a maximum volume of 50 l/min for air, 15 l/min for hydrogen and 2 l/min for methane at reference conditions of $0^\circ C$ and 1 atm. This enables flames with thermal powers of up to 2.5 kW for pure hydrogen combustion. The accuracy of the MFCs has been checked using a Bronkhorst Coriflow as a reference.

Figure 1: From left to right: Schematic view of the burner, fuel is supplied via the tube at the bottom, air is supplied via the tube on the side. Sectional view of the nozzles: N00, N01, N02 and an image of the flame during operation.

2.2. Numerical Optimization and Additive Manufacturing

Due to recirculation effects, the local mixture composition and cold gas speed are significantly influenced by the bluff-body [26]. Using such a design to increase the homogeneity of the gas mixture, NO_x formation was significantly decreased. Vance and Scholtissek [27] observed that a radial mixture stratification of the flow field effectively reduces the flash-back propensity therefore increasing the stability of hydrogen flames. This is primarily caused by locally reduced flame speeds due to leaner mixtures close to the burner wall. The stratification also results in a significant reduction of the thermal load on the burner, as the heat release in the flame is shifted towards its tip, reducing the thermal flux to the burner material [27, 32]. Targeting a radial mixture stratification and a high mixture homogeneity in the angular direction, burner designs are generated using a simulation-based optimization process. Strickling et al. [32] analyzed such burner designs using LES with adaptive mesh refinement for the flame zone and detailed chemistry. The stabilization behavior and the NO_x emissions of the flame were evaluated. Following the proposed

nozzle burner design principles by Vance et al. [27] and applying simulation-based shape optimization, additional burner geometries that produce the radially stratified mixtures are generated.

Additive manufacturing was identified as the most suitable method for creating these shapes. Here, laser powder bed fusion is an ideal tool as it enables a high degree of freedom of complex geometries compared to conventional manufacturing methods [33]. Additionally, the ability of rapid prototyping is advantageous for the creation of a large number of different burner nozzle geometries. For the burner nozzles an austenitic stainless steel 1.4404 (316L) was used, which is one of the most commonly used materials in AM. Although applying AM results in increased surface roughness of the burner parts, which was determined with a Ra value of $12\ \mu\text{m}$, an influence on flame topology and flow characteristics was found to be negligible. Three different nozzles were manufactured for this study, they are depicted in Figure 1: on the left there is the design N00 by Schmidt et al. [26], in the middle the numerically optimized design N01, characterized in Strickling et al. [32] and on the right a newer stratified design N02. For N02 the bluff-body is centered directly in the nozzle, as previous tests have demonstrated that the bluff-body can cause asymmetries in the flame if it is not properly centered [34]. When comparing the nozzles in the reactive large eddy simulations (LES), different LMHR can be observed, as evidenced in upcoming Figure 5 on the right. The LES are conducted following the same modeling approach as detailed in [32]. The main location of the heat release of N00 is close to the nozzle outlet. For N01 the stratification of the fuel mixture leads to a shift of the heat release location towards the flame tip. However, due to the radial mixture variations additional heat release also remains in the base of the flame. N02 (not shown) also represents a stratified concept.

3. Methods

To investigate the flames produced by the different nozzle designs, multiple optical diagnostics were utilized. An overview of the optical setup is depicted in Figure 2. The diagnostics are placed around the centered burner nozzle (9) and enable infrared (IR) thermometry as well as simultaneous OH and CH_2O planar laser-induced fluorescence or high-speed OH^* -chemiluminescence measurements.

Figure 2: Schematic of the optical diagnostics. The PLIF measurements were taken with both cameras simultaneously, for the chemiluminescence measurements, one of the cameras was replaced with an intensified high-speed camera Phantom v2012.

3.1. IR-Thermometry for the Nozzle Temperature

An IR-camera Optris Xi400 (13) with a spectral range from $7.5\text{-}13\ \mu\text{m}$ was used to measure the nozzle temperature T_{Noz} . A polyimide sticker with a known emission coefficient of 0.95 was used for calibration and ensuring reliable temperature recordings close to the nozzle outlet. Additionally, tests were performed on the reliability of this approach by controlling the temperature using a heating plate, the observation angle and employing different surface roughnesses of cube samples from the nozzle material. The latter two aspects did not show a significant impact on the determined temperature. However, we observed thermal degradation of the stickers for temperatures exceeding

250 °C. For all our investigated cases the maximum temperatures of the nozzles stayed below this critical temperature. The measurement location at the nozzle was approx. 1 mm below the nozzle outlet, as illustrated in Figure 4 on the left and marked by the black cross symbol. The elongated rectangular section in the image marks the polyimide sticker. To ensure steady state conditions in thermal equilibrium, the recordings were taken after a 10 minutes burn-in period, after which no further changes in the temperature could be observed.

3.2. Planar Laser-Induced Fluorescence

Paul and Najm [28] have observed that for methane/air flames the HRR of an unsteady reacting flow can be imaged as the product of formaldehyde and hydroxyl PLIF images. Recently, there have been studies that have proven this technique in CH₄/H₂-air mixtures for a variety of burner geometries [35, 36, 37]. We therefore adopted the approach of simultaneous OH and CH₂O planar laser-induced fluorescence to visualize the heat release location. For the OH-PLIF a Nd:YAG Quanta-Ray pulse laser (1) emitting at 532 nm was used for pumping a Sirah Cobra dye laser (2). As dye, Rhodamine 6G solved in ethanol was utilized, resulting in a fluorescence emission at 566 nm. This emission was then frequency-doubled to 283 nm, with a pulse energy in the probe volume of around 1.2 mJ, and excited the $A^2\Sigma^+ \leftarrow X^2\Pi(1, 0)Q_1(6)$ transition of OH radicals commonly used for OH imaging [38]. For the CH₂O-PLIF a Quantel Qsmart-450 frequency-tripled pulse-laser (3) emitting at 355 nm with a pulse energy of 61 mJ excited the $A^2A_1 \leftarrow X_1A^1 4_0^1pQ$ transition [38]. Both PLIF-lasers were operated at 10 Hz and were synchronized with the cameras using a Quantum Composers 9618 pulse generator. The 283 nm pulse was first reflected by a mirror (5) to align it correctly with the dichroic mirror (6). This dichroic mirror reflected the 283 nm laser and transmitted the 355 nm laser, combining both laser beams. For maximum reflectance of the dye laser a $\lambda/4$ -plate was used to adjust the polarization. After this the beam path was adjusted by a periscope (7) consisting of broadband UV-prisms as they have a higher damage threshold for both laser wavelength compared to mirrors. Finally, the beams were expanded by three cylindrical lenses (8) ($f_1 = 41$ mm ; $f_2 = 310$ mm ; $f_3 = 500$ mm). This resulted in a quasi light-sheet of approx. 200 μ m width in the focus, which is positioned in the center of the burner. For the OH-PLIF detection an iStar DH334T camera (10) and a 307-14 nm band-pass filter equipped on a B. Halle OUC 2.50 100 mm objective lens were utilized. For CH₂O-PLIF an iStar-IsCMOS (11) and a 450-100 nm band-pass filter in combination with a 100 mm Halle UV objective lens was used. The gating time of both cameras was set to 30 ns. For each flame, 150 images with an image size of 640x540 px for the CH₂O images and 512x512 px for the OH images were captured.

The image processing started with subtracting the background image taken without a laser pulse. Next, a laser-sheet correction (due to spatial intensity differences in the laser-sheet) was applied, based on images of a cuvette filled with fluorescing dye solution, which was placed in the measurement volume. In the following, a target was placed in the measurement volume to enable image registration of both cameras. Recordings of a scaled transparent target enabled the conversion of pixel values into real-world coordinates and the determination of the field of view. Finally, the OH images were transformed to fit the CH₂O image coordinates. An edge-aware filtering approach was applied to the normalized CH₂O signal to isolate the flame front and improve the robustness of the HRR estimation. First, the normalized CH₂O field was smoothed using a Gaussian filter ($\sigma = 1$ pixel) to support the following edge detection. To identify the flame front a Canny edge detection algorithm [39] with empirically selected threshold values (0.25–0.65) was utilized. To eliminate detected structures apart from the flame front, an area opening procedure was applied, removing connected components smaller than 20 pixels. To obtain the mask for the reaction zone, a distance transform was computed from the detected flame front. This distance field was then converted into a smooth weighting function using a Gaussian kernel with a standard deviation of $\sigma = 6$ pixels. The normalized CH₂O field was then multiplied by this mask to extract the flame front. A median filter of 3x3 pixels was also applied to the extracted CH₂O field to get rid of any persisting salt-and-pepper noise in the area of the detected flame front. The HRR was then estimated as the product of the normalized OH and filtered CH₂O signals. To suppress low-intensity noise, a threshold of 0.10 was applied, setting all lower values to zero.

3.3. Chemiluminescence

High-speed OH*-chemiluminescence imaging is commonly used in hydrogen flames to determine the flame topology, capture the reaction zone [40] and highlight fluctuations or oscillations in flames [41]. Additionally, the intensity of the OH* emission can be used as a marker for the HRR [29, 30]. Chemiluminescence generally requires less equipment than PLIF, especially for high-speed measurements. However, the main limitations of chemiluminescence

measurements are the line-of-sight integration of the three-dimensional flame and its qualitative nature. High-speed recordings of the OH* chemiluminescence signal in the flames were captured. To ensure the same viewing angle of the flame, the OH-PLIF camera (10) was replaced by a Phantom v2012 intensified camera (12), filtered with a 307-14 nm bandpass filter. We are aware that, for methane-containing flames, CH* may interfere with the OH* signal. However, since it appears similarly to OH* in the reaction front, it remains a second-order effect for the subsequent evaluation. The intensifier was set to a gating time of 90 μ s and an image rate of 10 kHz. 1000 images with an image size of 512x576 px were taken for each configuration. The camera objective lens was a B. Halle OUC 2.50 with a focal length of 100 mm and f/2. Background recordings without the flames were taken and subtracted from the flame images.

3.4. NIR-Thermometry for the Flame Temperatures

Near Infrared (NIR) thermometry was performed using a sensor developed in [42] and schematically depicted in Figure 2 (14). Two 2" parabolic mirrors (15) collect the flame emissions from a measurement volume of 0.4 mm FWHM diameter and an axial extension of 3.9 mm FWHM. Two photodiodes (Thorlabs PDA10CS2) measure the emission of water molecules in a range from 1300 nm to 1500 nm and 1500 nm to 1700 nm, respectively. Similar approaches were presented by Nakaya et al. [43] and Zhou et al. [44]. Compared to our setup, both studies used spectrometers for the spectral separation resulting in longer acquisition times compared to the photodiodes. Here, the spectral separation is achieved by combining a 1300 nm longpass filter and a 1500 nm shortpass dichroic mirror. The gain for both diodes was set to 1.5×10^6 V A⁻¹. The read-out of the diode signal was performed using a Keysight InfiniVision DSO-X 4054 A oscilloscope, measuring at 31.25 kHz. The ratio of the measured voltages of both diodes was then interpreted by comparing it to calibration measurements of known flames, taken in a McKenna burner [42]. Since the diagnostic performs particularly well in the product zone of the flame, where the water content is high, a height above burner (HAB) of 15 mm was identified as a suitable measurement location based on the OH* images.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Flame Stability Maps

Figure 3: Upper row: Flame stability maps of the extinction limits of all three nozzles for different hydrogen/methane mixtures. Blue areas are stable flame conditions while red parts result in blow-outs or flash-back. The operating points for upcoming discussions are marked by black \times symbols. The flash-back limit is marked with "FB" and blow-out limits with "BO". Bottom row: Flame stability maps of the extinction limits for different powers of the burner for $Y_{H_2}=1.0$.

The first step to assess the performance of a nozzle is the investigation of the extinction limits. By discovering the flash-back and lean blow-out (LBO) limits for different equivalence ratios ϕ and different mass ratios of the H₂/CH₄

Table 1: Overview of the measurement points with fuel mass fractions hydrogen/methane, equivalence ratios and volume flow rates. Additionally, combustion parameters calculated by Cantera are given.

Name	Y_{H_2}	Y_{CH_4}	ϕ	$\dot{V}_{H_2} /$ $l \text{ min}^{-1}$	$\dot{V}_{CH_4} /$ $l \text{ min}^{-1}$	$\dot{V}_{Air} /$ $l \text{ min}^{-1}$	$s_L /$ $m \text{ s}^{-1}$	Re	T_{ad} / K
H0.20_PHI0.9	20	80	0.9	2.08	1.05	16.59	0.69	3193	2191
H0.20_PHI1.0			1.0			14.93	0.80	2894	2279
H0.20_PHI1.1			1.1			13.57	0.85	2650	2277
H0.30_PHI0.8	30	70	0.8	2.81	0.83	18.21	0.70	3463	2079
H0.30_PHI0.9			0.9			16.18	0.88	3099	2212
H0.30_PHI1.0			1.0			14.56	1.02	2808	2299
H0.30_PHI1.1			1.1			13.24	1.12	2570	2301
H0.40_PHI0.8	40	60	0.8	3.41	0.65	17.83	0.85	3379	2098
H0.40_PHI0.9			0.9			15.85	1.07	3023	2229
H0.40_PHI1.0			1.0			14.27	1.25	2738	2316
H0.40_PHI1.1			1.1			12.97	1.38	2504	2321
H1.00_PHI0.7	100	0	0.7	5.56	0	18.93	1.19	3508	2012
H1.00_PHI0.8			0.8			16.56	1.61	3084	2167
H1.00_PHI1.0			1.0			13.25	2.28	2492	2380

mixtures, an overall estimation of the fuel flexibility and operating range can be made. The operating range is mostly linked to the stability of the flames. The extinction limits can be found experimentally by gradually changing the air-flow for constant fuel mass-flows for a set power output of 1 kW, which is defined by the heating value and mass flow of the fuel. The fuel mass fraction of hydrogen Y_{H_2} was increased in steps of 0.1. This results in a stability map of the burner depicting the operating ranges in the equivalence ratio ϕ for each burner nozzle, these are pictured in Figure 3 in the upper row. The blue areas reflect stable operating points, the red zones are unstable operating points resulting in immediate or delayed extinction. Within these operation ranges, 14 operating points were selected for this study, as summarized in Table 1 and also marked by the black symbols in Figure 3. These are mostly mixtures at or below a Y_{H_2} of 0.4, which is the highest mass fraction of hydrogen containing sufficient amounts of CH_2O for PLIF measurements. Additionally, lean cases were selected due to their relevance for most technical applications. As the burners are optimized for the use of pure hydrogen, Y_{H_2} of 1.0 was also included. From 1D Cantera simulations the adiabatic flame temperatures T_{ad} , Reynolds numbers Re and flame speeds s_L for the operating points were calculated, and these are listed in Table 1. The Reynolds numbers reveal that the flames are mostly in a transitional flow regime. All 14 flames were operated at a constant power output of 1 kW. All measurements had a burn in time of several minutes to reach steady state conditions.

The maps in the bottom row of Figure 3 were taken by decreasing the power in steps of 0.1 kW from 1.2 kW to 0.4 kW for pure H_2 , revealing the correlation between the power and the extinction limits. By comparing the operating ranges for different fuel mixtures, assumptions on the stability of the flames and the fuel flexibility of the burners can be made. The flame stability map for the reference nozzle N00 shows a broad range, with the flash-back limit as the upper line. It moves from lean to rich conditions with decreasing hydrogen content. In contrast, the LBO limit (lower line) is moving towards lean operating points for higher hydrogen content. Nozzle N01 has a narrower flame stability map compared to N00 with flash-back limits moving towards leaner flames and also LBO limits moving towards richer flames. This indicates an increased flash-back propensity for this nozzle, as well as limited performance for lean conditions, leading to blow-outs. Nozzle N02 exhibits the broadest flame stability map. The LBO is similar to N00 and the flash-back limit is increased to higher ϕ for all mixtures. This optimized nozzle outperforms the nozzles N00 and N01 in terms of fuel-flexibility and flame stability, i.e. flash-back and blow-out limits. The dependence of the limits on power, pictured in Figure 3 in the bottom row, outlines similar trends for all three nozzles. N02 performs best, followed by N00 and N01. In the maps, the LBO can be seen on the left side of the stable operating range, with an almost linear gradient moving towards richer points for higher power flames. This means the LBO limit decreases with increasing power. Similar results have been obtained by Griebel et al. [45], where this effect was hypothesized to be caused by an increased flame stretch due to higher velocity gradients between the flame and the recirculation

zone. For our experiments, an increasing flame stretch could be caused by increasing turbulence or higher variations in the local mixture field with higher mass-flows. For the flash-back limit there is an exponential like increase in ϕ with increasing power. The gradient is steeper for N00 and N01, while N02 starts increasing steadily to higher ϕ at lower powers, resulting in the highest flash-back limits. The comparison of the flame stability maps reveals that the nozzle N02 performs best with respect to LBO and flash-back, across all powers and different fuel mixtures. N02 and N01 (which performs worst) are both intentionally stratified concepts with a fuel rich core and a lean annulus. N00 also shows radial mixture variations, however, the fuel rich locations are located at the edges of flow. Our working hypothesis is that the stability of the flames is mainly influenced by the location of the heat release.

4.2. IR-Thermometry for the Nozzle Temperature

An indicator for heat release close to the nozzle outlet is the temperature of the nozzle itself, which is influenced by the feedback of the flame into the nozzle. For the IR measurements thermodynamic equilibrium of the nozzles has to be reached, which is realized by continuous operation for 10 minutes at the start and 2 minutes between each operating point. Figure 4 demonstrates an IR-image obtained by the Xi400 camera with the measurement area for the temperature marked by the black cross. The polyimide sticker is visible in form of the brighter rectangular stripe. All temperature readings outside these regions are affected by an unknown emission coefficient of the steel and thus only provide a qualitative picture. The temperature data was acquired for a time period of up to 30 seconds. The resulting time-averaged temperature in a range from 313 K to 433 K is displayed in the diagram on the right for the various operating points. Nozzle N01 (yellow) has the lowest T_{Noz} , N02 (red) reaches similar temperatures being consistently 5 K to 10 K above N01. N00 (blue) reaches the highest temperatures, being around 15 to 35 K above N01. There seems to be a correlation between the nozzle temperature and the stability. This might be explained by two reasons. First, T_{Noz} directly influences the extinction limits. Especially for the LBO, the flame can be stabilized by increased anchoring to the burner outlet. A similar effect was already noted by Kedia et al.[46]. This study indicated that for bluff-body stabilized flames a sufficiently high bluff-body temperature and an improved mixture composition can result in the establishment of favorable anchoring conditions close to the bluff-body. This would explain the increased LBO limit for N00 due to improved anchoring conditions caused by high T_{Noz} . Additionally, N02 seems to perform even better, although the temperatures are a few Kelvin lower. This may be caused by the stratification of the mixture field resulting in improved mixture compositions for the anchoring. The second reason is the influence of the heat release zone directly on the stability of the flame. The burner temperature is directly linked to the region of LMHR by the heat flux from the flame to the burner material. To confirm this link, additional measurements are required to visualize the heat release zone. As mentioned in Section 3.2, one of the most commonly used methods for this is simultaneous OH and CH₂O PLIF.

Figure 4: Left: IR-image taken with the Optris Xi400 camera, the black cross symbol indicates the measurement region for the right side plot. The polyimide sticker is marked with the white rectangle. Right: Average T_{Noz} .

4.3. Planar Laser-Induced Fluorescence

Figure 5 exhibits the PLIF images of flames with $Y_{H_2} = 0.3$, $\phi = 1.0$ and a thermal power of 1 kW. The upper row of the images is for nozzle N00, while the bottom row depicts the PLIF recordings for N01. On the left side, the corrected and masked CH₂O images are shown with a narrow zone of CH₂O directly before the flame front.

CH₂O is mainly formed by fuel breakdown processes occurring during low temperature oxidation. The location of the highest formaldehyde concentration in flames is highlighted by numerous publications [47, 38, 48], which observed comparable results. In the center left of Figure 5 the processed OH-PLIF images are depicted, showing the concentration of OH, which begins to form in the flame front and persists into the post reaction zone. As Paul and Najm [28] have investigated, the heat release rate can be derived from the product of the OH and CH₂O images, this is illustrated in Figure 5 on the center right side. This figure represents the HRR in the flame front for methane/hydrogen mixtures. The locations with highest intensities in the image are proportional to the highest heat release. The single-shot HRR images confirm the computation of the heat release by the numerical simulations. The topology and intensity of the HRR image is a good fit for the computed HRR, which are depicted in Figure 5 on the right. For a comparison of the axial location of the highest heat release for the three nozzles, the intensity centroid of the HRR images is calculated. Its axial (y-) coordinate is obtained by

$$y_{\text{Centroid}} = \frac{\sum_{y=1}^H \sum_{x=1}^W y \cdot S(x, y)}{\sum_{y=1}^H \sum_{x=1}^W S(x, y)}, \quad (1)$$

where y_{Centroid} is the intensity centroid in the axial direction, y is the y-coordinate of a pixel, $S(x, y)$ is the intensity for each pixel. H is the image height and W is the image width, in this study 512 px and 576 px, respectively. The centroid can also be calculated for the radial direction, expressing the location of the highest heat release from the images in one quantity/point. This facilitates comparison between the nozzles for different operating conditions. For the cases exemplified in Figure 5, the y_{Centroid} is located at HAB=8.3 mm for N00, at 8.4 mm for N01 and at 7.6 mm for N02, which is also depicted in Figure 7 on the left. Here, the blue symbols represent the y-centroid for the HRR. The standard deviation around the mean for all three cases is comparable with approx. 0.75 mm. In this context, the flame lengths for all cases have to be considered, which are taken from the chemiluminescence images in 6 and show that N01 is about 1 mm shorter than N00. This means that the LMHR for this nozzle is located more downstream, as anticipated by the numerical calculations of the HRR. This supports the link of the LMHR location to T_{Noz} . The further upstream the heat release occurs, the higher T_{Noz} , as there is presumably a stronger heat transfer to the nozzle. The major downside of the PLIF approach is related to hydrogen rich cases. Beyond $Y_{H_2}=0.4$ the formaldehyde signal-to-noise ratio becomes too low to evaluate the HRR. This highlights the need for another diagnostic method to reveal the LMHR location for such cases.

4.4. Chemiluminescence

As mentioned in Section 3.3, a possible alternative to PLIF measurements is the local intensity distribution of the OH*-chemiluminescence. The chemiluminescence intensity of OH* radicals depends on pressure, strain rate, equivalence ratio and turbulence level [49]. In this study, the effects of these parameters are considered of minor importance and we link the intensity mainly to a series of elementary reactions, modeling OH* formation and depletion:

Based on these equations, the concentration of OH* is a strong indicator of the flame front and the heat release rate [40]. Figure 6 displays this marker in three consecutive images from a high-speed time-series. The series confirms the transitional flow regime of the flame front. By temporal averaging of 1000 images the average flame topology can be resolved. In general, the flames are axis-symmetric. For some of the leaner cases, the flame anchors preferentially to one side of the nozzle. The location of the anchoring is dependent on the equivalence ratio and can flip from one side to the other. Further investigations indicate that the centering of the bluff-body inside the nozzle is the decisive parameter for this asymmetry, especially as the nozzle N02, more dedicatedly centered in the manufacturing process, shows fewer asymmetries [34]. Additionally, the chemiluminescence measurements indicate that the flame length of the nozzles is dependent on the global equivalence ratio, linked through the ratio of flame speed and bulk flow velocity [50, 51, 52]. The flame length is also dependent on the bluff-body geometry since the local mixture field significantly influences the flame length, as indicated in [32]. For a robust comparison of the height of the heat release relative to the flame, the flame length has to be taken into account. Similar to the procedure in Section 4.3, the intensity centroid

Figure 5: Top Row: PLIF images of N00 at $Y_{H_2}=0.3$ and a ϕ of 1.0, From left to right: CH_2O , OH, Heat-Release-Rate, Simulated HRR [32]. Bottom Row: PLIF Images of N02 at $Y_{H_2}=0.3$ and a ϕ of 1.0, From left to right: CH_2O , OH, Heat-Release-Rate, Simulated HRR [32].

of the OH^* intensity was calculated as the area of the maximum heat release. To decouple the dependence on the changing flame length and to gain a robust size for quantifying the location of the LMHR, the ratio of the intensity centroid in the axial direction to the flame length was determined (C/L -ratio). For the large number of images across all configurations, an automated evaluation routine for determining the C/L -ratio was required. The flame height was calculated by compressing the images into a vertical profile and finding the elbow of the intensity profile by using a two-segment linear regression method. The profile region above the intensity maximum was iteratively split into two segments, and each segment was fitted using least-squares linear regression. The split point that minimized the combined sum of squared fitting errors was identified as the elbow position. This proved to be a robust fit for the flame length. As there can be significant fluctuations in the flame length over an image series, this calculation was done for each single shot, increasing the accuracy of the fit. In Figure 6 on the right, an averaged image is depicted. The blue cross marks the location of the intensity centroid of the HRR images from PLIF measurements, the red cross the intensity centroid from chemiluminescence and the green line the computed flame length. The intensity centroids for both HRR and chemiluminescence images show sufficient agreement, which is demonstrated for multiple methane/hydrogen flames in Figure 7 on the left. The resulting trends are comparable between both methods. This shows that the OH^* -chemiluminescence can be utilized as a surrogate for LMHR determination and will also be used for pure hydrogen cases. The resulting C/L -ratios for all 14 configurations are illustrated in Figure 7 on the right for each nozzle. To recall, if the C/L -ratio is higher, the HRR is located more towards the tip of the flame, while for lower values it is located closer to the nozzle. The figure confirms the trends observed in the PLIF measurements, also for the pure hydrogen cases. Identical to the PLIF images, the heat release for N00 (blue) is the furthest upstream. For N01 (yellow) it is closest to the flame tip, while N02 (red) lies in between. The trends for the heat release are also consistent in the pure hydrogen cases, with a sharp increase towards $\phi = 1.0$. Here, the flame speed is comparably high (see Table 1), resulting in a short flame length and therefore a higher C/L value. This point is already close to flash-back. The flame height drastically decreases close to the rich extinction limit, so far until flash-back occurs.

Figure 6: From the left: Three consecutive high-speed chemiluminescence images at 10 kHz of Nozzle 00 for 30 % hydrogen and a ϕ of 1.0, averaged chemiluminescence image with the intensity centroid in red, the intensity centroid of the PLIF-HRR images in blue and the detected flame length in green.

Figure 7: Left: Comparison of the y-centroid position for OH* and the HRR images, Right: C/L-Ratio for all 14 flame configurations of Table 1.

4.5. NIR-Emission Ratiometry

The heat release location and the feedback into the nozzle might be directly linked to the flame temperatures. When measuring at a fixed height above the burner in the post reaction zone, the temperatures should increase towards $\phi = 1.0$ and increase for higher hydrogen mass fractions. This aligns with the adiabatic temperatures from Table 1, however, due to the varying heat loss to the nozzles adiabatic conditions are unlikely and temperature measurements are required. To determine flame temperatures, the NIR-thermometry setup measures the ratio of two water emission bands, which follows the temperature according to Boltzmann's distribution. Reliable temperatures can mainly be measured in the post reaction zone, with the presence of sufficient amounts of water molecules as the combustion product. The chemiluminescence measurements revealed that there is a difference in flame lengths for the different conditions. Based on these recordings, HAB 15 mm was identified as an appropriate measurement location in the post-oxidation region, providing a sufficient amount of water in the measurement volume especially when focusing on hydrogen rich cases. The mean value of the resulting flame temperatures can be seen in Figure 8. The general trends for the flame temperatures for different fuel mixtures and equivalence ratios are comparable to the trends of the adiabatic flame temperature in Table 1. Additionally, the general temperature trends follow those of T_{Noz} from Figure 4, which are also increasing with ϕ and Y_{H_2} . However, when comparing the trends for the different nozzles, an inverse behavior can be observed. The nozzles with the highest T_{Noz} (N00 and N02) have the lowest flame temperatures, likely due to the heat loss to the burner nozzle. This observation also aligns with the C/L-ratios, which are closer to the nozzles for both conditions. Finally, there are also implications of the flame temperature on pollutant formation, especially the thermal NO_x emissions. Increasing flame temperatures should result in increasing NO_x levels.

Figure 8: Flame temperatures in K measured with the NIR-diode setup at HAB = 15 mm.

4.6. NO_x Emission Measurements

The concentration of nitrous oxides in the exhaust gas was determined using an MRU Optima handheld emission meter. The measurements are presented in Figure 9 and based on 15 % O_2 . The burner was housed in a combustion chamber and the exhaust gas was sampled. The NO_x results indicate the similar trends as the C/L-ratio of the chemiluminescence measurements, as well as the flame temperatures. N00 (blue) has (with one exception) the lowest NO_x emissions of all three nozzles, while for N01 the highest emissions can be observed. The overall difference between N00 and N01 are around 10 ppm for most of the investigated operating points. Comparing this to the influence of the equivalence ratio, the difference between $\phi=1.0$ and $\phi=0.8$ is around 20 to 40 ppm, depending on Y_{H_2} . Lean conditions decrease the flame temperatures significantly, thus reducing the thermal NO_x formation accordingly. These results imply that for the minimum achievable NO_x emissions, the LBO-limit is the governing parameter. When comparing different nozzles under the same operating conditions, the differences in the NO_x emissions are relatively small (10 ppm). In contrast, changing the operating point to leaner conditions has a much greater effect. The more stable a flame is for lean conditions, the further the equivalence ratio can be decreased. This results in a strong decrease of the flame temperature, leading to a stronger decline in NO_x formation. This indicates that nozzle N02 is capable of achieving the lowest NO_x emissions as it has the leanest blow-out limit.

Figure 9: NO_x emissions in ppm measured by the MRU Optima and based on 15 % O_2 .

5. Conclusions and Outlook

A comparison of the three numerically optimized and additively manufactured nozzles reveals clear trends and correlations among the investigated parameters. Table 2 shows a summary of the different quantities at the operating point $Y_{H_2} = 1.0$ and $\phi = 0.8$. The results of the flame stability maps for different fuel mixtures and equivalence ratios show that nozzle N02 has the broadest operating range. N00 follows while nozzle N01 has a significantly reduced operating range. Based on these findings and the numerical simulations, we could conclude that the location of the maximum heat release zone has a strong influence on the stability of the flames and the extinction limits. Infrared thermometry indicated that higher nozzle temperatures increase the range of the operating ranges. This suggested a potential influence on flame stability through either direct thermal effects at the nozzle or variations in the axial position of peak heat release and the resulting thermal feedback. To further investigate this working hypothesis, OH and CH₂O PLIF measurements were used to visualize the heat release rate. The results demonstrated that the heat release location is closest to the burner outlet for N00, with N02 showing a similar but slightly more downstream position. The LMHR zone of N01 is most downstream and located close to the flame tip. As formaldehyde PLIF is only possible for methane/hydrogen mixtures up to a methane mass fraction of 0.4, an additional diagnostic was needed for pure hydrogen cases. Here, high-speed OH*-chemiluminescence was used. The relative location of the maximum heat release was quantified using the ratio of the axial intensity centroid to the total flame length (C/L-ratio). The resulting C/L-ratio graph illustrates the same trends as T_{Noz} for all cases investigated in this study, linking both quantities. Quasi-point measurements of the flame temperature were determined using a ratiometric approach of the NIR-emission of water molecules. The flame temperatures align with the findings of the other diagnostics.

Table 2: Summary of all nozzles for $Y_{H_2} = 1.0$, $\phi = 0.8$ and a thermal power of 1 kW

Nozzle	OR for $Y_{H_2}=1.0$ in ϕ	T_{Noz} in K	C/L	T_{Flm} in K	NO_x in ppm
00	0.6-1.2	387	0.591 ± 0.02	2100 ± 88	12
01	0.5-0.9	354	0.617 ± 0.03	2188 ± 148	17
02	0.35-1.3	366	0.607 ± 0.04	2125 ± 137	14

It is difficult to separate the influence of the LMHR from that of an increased T_{Noz} . The measurements nevertheless show that lower LMHR correlates with reduced flame tip temperatures. It is hypothesized that the increase in the burner temperature influences the unburnt gas resulting in changes in the complex interplay of chemistry, turbulence and flame speed, which enables the flame to operate in an increased range of equivalence ratios for different powers and fuel mixtures. The exact mechanism for the stabilization has not been subject of this study, but further investigations involving kinetic mechanisms would certainly be highly interesting. This behaviour especially explains the poor performance of N01. The comparison between N00 and N02 indicates that additional mechanisms are involved beyond the location of the heat release. It is suggested that effects of the radial mixture stratification play a role resulting in favorable anchoring conditions for the numerically optimized N02. In addition to stability and burner flexibility, pollutant formation was investigated as another optimization objective. It was found that NO_x emissions are mainly linked to T_{Noz} and low emissions can be realized for conditions with pronounced heat transfer from the flame to the burner material. It was also proven that the overall influence of the equivalence ratio on the flame temperature outweighs geometrical changes at a constant global equivalence ratio. Increasing the operating range of a nozzle towards leaner conditions is therefore an effective measure for decreasing the NO_x formation, making it a good optimization target.

To differentiate the effects of the heat release and increased T_{Noz} in future studies, the investigation of a temperature-regulated nozzles is proposed. This can also be achieved by additive manufacturing, integrating heating elements or cooling channels directly into the nozzle. While this study is limited to optimized designs for single nozzles, the effect of multiple adjacent nozzles and the interplay between flames should be investigated in future studies.

Author contributions:

S.R.F.: Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Visualization, Writing - Original Draft.

N.S.: Methodology, Investigation.

F.T.: Investigation, Software, Formal analysis.

R.S.: Software, Resources, Validation, Writing - Review and Editing.

J.S.: Software, Resources, Writing - Review and Editing.

D.B.: Supervision.

F.H.V.: Supervision.

M.S.: Project administration, Funding acquisition.

A.S.: Conceptualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

F.J.B.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Supervision, Writing - Review and Editing.

S.W.: Conceptualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Writing - Review and Editing.

Data availability:

The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT and DeepL to assist with visualization by generating MATLAB code for plots and for translation and language refinement. After using this tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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